

GENERAL LITERARY REVIEW ON THE PROBLEM OF MOTIVATING YOUNG READER

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the importance of the work is that the thorough analysis of motivating young readers in EFL classes and there are given main reading types which can prove the ways of motivation.

All human behavior is performed with a purpose and is the result of certain motives which arise from either internal (physiological) or external (environmental) stimuli. Motivation can therefore be defined as "the process of activating, maintaining and directing behavior toward a particular goal", and this behavior tends to stop after the desired goal is obtained. Motivation is a phenomenon which cannot be observed, and because of this, psychologists and researchers must draw conclusions about what it is and what causes it. The question, "What motivates a person to do a particular thing" is usually asking "Why does a person behave the way that he does?" In other words, motivation refers to the cause of behavior.

If teachers are to create optimal learning environments, they must address their students' interests, beliefs, concerns and needs- in other words, their students' motivations. It has been said that "We need to stop asking 'How motivated are my students?' and start asking 'How are my students motivated?'"

Before we get into specific methods, it should be useful to analyze some scientific opinions and examine what motivation is, what it does, and how it works.

Motivation has emerged as a multifaceted construct that involves the interaction of multiple personal, social, and achievement outcomes[10;313],generating diverse profiles of motivation.[13;126]However, a comprehensive portrait of motivation and an understanding of how motivation constructs work together and conflict remains necessary in order to fully understand motivation and its relationship with academic achievement.[11;53]

Motivation is what drives you toward a goal, what keeps you going when things get tough, the reason you get up early to exercise or work late to finish a project. There are all kinds of motivations, of course, from positive to negative.

According to today's top motivational theories, the subject of motivation can be broken

up into two main types, which include intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation:

In education psychology a distinction is usually made between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, the former being sometimes thought to relate to long-term success. Intrinsic motivation is usually defined as a motivation guided by an interesting in the task itself in which one is engaged. Intrinsic motivation as one for which there is no apparent reward except the activity itself. People seem to engage in the activities for their own sake and not because they lead to an extrinsic reward. Intrinsically motivation behaviors are aimed at bringing out certain internally rewarding consequences, namely, feeling of competence and self-determination.

On the other hand, extrinsically motivated behaviors are carried out in anticipation of a reward from outside and beyond the self. It is said be guided by external stimulus, such as to get the parental approval, a reward, a good grade, etc. Behaviors initiated to avoid punishment are also extrinsically motivated. The relationship between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation is just like that between internal and external causes. Materialist dialectics holds that external causes become operative through internal causes. Traditionally, schools were fraught with extrinsically motivation behavior, influenced by behaviorism.

Teaching material, parents and teachers' wishes are all forced onto students, whether they like them or not. From extrinsic to intrinsic motivation in education institutions depicts what can happen in an institution and turns the extrinsic pressure into an intrinsically oriented direction.

A comprehensive definition of motivation implies pre-decisional, self-directed movement towards a particular learning goal.[13;158] Pintrich stated that research on how motivation changes and develops over time is a necessary direction for this field. Within Rheinberg, Vollmeyer, and Rollet's framework, motivation affects the strength and quality of commitment towards learning goals. Pintrich specified five motivational generalizations regarding the cognitive constructs that motivate students towards academic goals: *adaptive self-efficacy and competence beliefs; adaptive attributions and control beliefs; higher levels of interest and intrinsic motivation; higher levels of value; and goals.*

Rheinberg and colleagues discussed motivational states as the characteristics of motivation during a learning phase, which are more likely to change than general motivational orientations.

Motivation consists of the biological, physiological, social, and cognitive forces that direct behaviour. Despite efforts of various approaches and methodologies to encapsulate the construct of motivation, a single approach is unable to capture its complexities. Resulting from this narrow focus and the absence of appropriate measures, the study of motivation remains theoretically fragmented and in the beginning stages of development.

Motivation guides all of us in everything we do each day. It is such an important part of our daily lives, yet there is still so much to be understood about it. One particular area of interest in motivation and its principles is in the field of education and what motivates students to learn. In general terms, student motivation refers to "a willingness, need, desire or even compulsion to participate in, and be successful in, the learning process". Students can be motivated to pay attention in class and

stay on task, to complete assignments and homework, to do well on tests, etc. Teachers, psychologists and researchers continue to study motivation, how it affects students, and how to encourage it to promote interest in learning at school.

It is difficult for students to learn if they do not have the motivation to do so, but two very different types of motivation guide their learning- extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic motivation refers to acts being performed to bring about a reward or to avoid an undesirable consequence. Intrinsic motivation, on the other hand, refers to acts being performed because they are satisfying or pleasurable in and of themselves.[2;6] Both types of motivation have their benefits and drawbacks in the classroom, but overall, researchers agree that intrinsic motivation is the more powerful tool.

Learning is most effective when a student is ready to learn, when he or she wants to know something. Sometimes the student's readiness and eagerness to learn evolve with time, and it is the teacher's role to encourage this development and help it continue. However, knowing that learning must be motivated and understanding the specifics of the motivations can sometimes be two very different things. Students come from different backgrounds with different life experiences, but there are often general ideas, which will be discussed later, that educators can keep in mind when deciding the best ways in which to teach students and give them valuable learning tools for the future.

Motivation is responsible for persistence and expended effort with atask.[7;519] Due to the importance that teachers and parents place on effort, young children believe effort to be one of the key indicators of academic competence, and that exerting effort will lead to increased ability. Young children do not understand the inverse relationship between effort and ability, perceiving themselves as less competent when required to work harder.

A large number of foreign language teachers have focused on extensive and intensive reading. Both approaches, widely researched and written about, offer distinct benefits in the development of foreign language reading skills.

Extensive reading. With extensive reading, learners read a large quantity of material within their linguistic level. For extensive reading to be possible and for it to have the desired results, texts must be well within the learners' reading competence in the foreign language.[6;136-141] Another important principle of extensive reading noted by many authors, Renandya and Jacobs is that large amounts of level-appropriate material must be read regularly.[14;295-302] A third key principle is that learners should have a wide variety of materials to choose from and have complete autonomy in the choice of readings. Autonomy and choice are often credited for increasing motivation levels and developing autonomous learners. Grabe referred to these and other benefits: "Longer concentrated periods of silent reading build vocabulary and structural awareness, develop automaticity, enhance background knowledge, improve comprehension skills, and promote confidence and motivation".[8;375]

Intensive reading. Intensive reading material includes many vocabulary items and possibly grammatical forms that are difficult or new to the student. The intent is for students to explicitly study new words and employ reading skills (e.g., skimming, scanning, and guessing meaning from context). Bruton described intensive reading as "having comprehension and language-focused tasks completed communally by the whole class".[5;23-

25] Brown similarly stated that intensive reading is usually “a classroom-oriented activity in which students focus on the linguistic or semantic details . . . grammatical forms, discourse markers, and other surface structure details for the purpose of understanding”. [9;357] Intensive reading is essential when learning a foreign language, but presents many challenges, especially in a group context.

Extrinsic motivation in the classroom

When students today are faced with assignments, they usually wonder one or both of the following questions: "What do I get if I do it?" or "What happens if I don't do it?" Both of these questions arise from extrinsic motivation. An extrinsically motivated student performs a task or assignment in order to receive some type of reward or to avoid some type of punishment external to the activity itself. Classroom practices designed by schools and teachers in an attempt to get students to learn often reinforce students' extrinsic motivation. There are numerous ways of providing rewards, such as publicly recognizing students for academic achievements, placing students on honor rolls, offering pizzas for reading, and giving out stickers or candy. Schools and teachers might also manipulate and encourage students' extrinsic motivation by taking away a privilege, such as recess, based on poor academic performance. [1;3-36]

While most would agree that classroom activities are often structured around extrinsic motivation as a means of getting students to learn, the question becomes “Is this good or bad?” Two important and rather well-known research studies have tried to answer this question. One was carried out by the psychologists Lepper, Green and Nisbett. They studied children who spent a high percentage of time drawing during free play. They took children individually and asked them to draw. Children in one group were shown a “good-player” certificate and told they could win one by drawing. After they drew, the children were told they had done well and were given the certificate. Children in another group were not told about the certificate, but after they drew, they were given the same feedback and certificate, to take into account any effect due to receiving a reward. A third group of children drew with no mention of a certificate and were not given one at the end, which controlled for any effect due to drawing. Two weeks later, the children were again observed during their free time to determine the amount of time they had spent drawing. While there was no significant difference in time spent drawing by children who were given unexpected rewards or no rewards at all during the initial observation, the children who expected a reward the first time spent less time drawing during the second observation than they did during the first.

Even though extrinsic motivation has been used in schools for years, there is little evidence to show that it encourages learning. Extrinsic motivation does give students goals and the students follow the rules of learning set up by the teacher when they want to “win the prize” of a good grade, sticker, recognition, etc. Unfortunately, students learn to view the information they need to learn and understand as a means to an end rather than something interesting to know on its own. Chances are they will not regard it as something useful in its own right and are therefore not likely to inquire further into the subject matter. Even worse, once students have received “the prize” they often no longer have any motivation to retain the information they have learned. Studies have also found that students who are naturally

curious when faced with an extrinsic reward do generate questions, but those questions often do not relate to the subject matter at hand. Instead, the questions on the minds of the students tend to relate to "How can I bend the rules to win the game?" or "What's the least amount of effort I can put in and still satisfy the teacher?"

Some research has shown that using extrinsic motivators to encourage student learning can both lower achievement and negatively affect student motivation. Students who are motivated to complete a task simply to avoid negative consequences or to earn a certain grade rarely put forth more than the minimum effort necessary to meet their goals. In addition, when students begin to focus on how their successes or failures compare to their classmates' rather than focusing on mastering skills at their own rate, they are more easily discouraged.

It is true that external rewards may keep students productive, but they also tend to decrease students' interest in an activity, and therefore the likelihood that the students will continue that activity on their own in the future. In this way, extrinsic motivation controls behavior, but only temporarily. In the reading classroom, for example, one might inform students that they must complete a specific task such as answering comprehension questions for a sticker or a good grade. When the students then complete the task with the knowledge of what external reward they will get in doing so, their on-task behavior will only be temporary because the reading activity will end once the goal has been reached. If students are reading to complete an assignment, the reading will stop when the task is completed. When teachers rely on extrinsic motivation in the classroom, they must provide a new goal or "reward" for each activity.

If a teacher insists upon using extrinsic motivation in the classroom, he or she should provide clear expectations, give corrective feedback and provide valuable rewards. These rewards should be used sparingly and are most effective when they are closely related to the activities at hand. Also, rewards should only be given when they are clearly deserved. Giving a prize or reward to a student who only puts a minimal amount of effort into an assignment sends the message to the student that the amount of effort is acceptable, and the reward then becomes meaningless. Finally, teachers must remember that extrinsic rewards will only work as long as students are under their control. When outside of their control, students will stop the behavior (of a learning activity, for example) unless it has been internalized and the students have become intrinsically motivated to continue learning on their own. The next chapters will discuss intrinsic motivation in more detail, including how and why it tends to be more effective in the classroom than extrinsic motivation.

Intrinsic motivation in the classroom

Many educational theorists claim that external rewards decrease the quality of students' work and create disinterest in topics that might otherwise be enjoyed and further pursued due to a personal interest in the subject matter. One psychologist has been quoted as saying, "Rewards are devastatingly effective in smothering enthusiasm for activities children might otherwise enjoy".[12;53]

As mentioned in previous chapters, extrinsic motivation arises from factors external to an individual. Tasks are performed to avoid negative consequences, or in anticipation of a reward which is artificially linked to the behavior. Intrinsic motivation, on the other hand,

arises from an internal drive to complete a task and the payoffs for intrinsically motivated behavior come directly from performing the behavior. A task is performed simply for the sake of doing it. For example, reading for pleasure and information would be considered intrinsically motivating, while reading to make a good grade, earn a privilege, or impress the teacher would be considered extrinsically motivating.[15;74]

Benefits of intrinsic motivation in students run across the board, and to imagine a room full of intrinsically motivated students, one could imagine the following scenario: The atmosphere in the classroom is one of excitement and anticipation. An overview of the room finds a group of students who are alert, curious, energized, eager to learn and working on task. The students do not need the teacher to remind them or even beg them to carry on with their work. They want to be in the classroom and are excited about learning. This scenario is one in

which most teachers only dream about and few are able to experience, but the key to help make it a reality is that of students who are intrinsically motivated.[3;46]

It is one thing to say that students should be intrinsically motivated, and another to ensure that they actually are. Many issues make the task of encouraging this motivation in students a challenging one, but when teachers take the time to understand what it is and implement helpful learning strategies, steps can be made.

A major issue working against intrinsic motivation relates to the developmental changes, both physical and psychological, that occur during the often difficult period of adolescence. In the middle elementary school years, students become very self-conscious and skeptical and may begin to doubt the value of their academic work and their abilities to succeed. This concern has become the focal point of many studies and unfortunately, findings associated with middle school learning consistently show a drop in students' intrinsic motivation. This downward trend in motivation can however, be avoided. Over the past decade, several researchers have concluded that difficulties arise because the typical learning environment in middle school is often mismatched with adolescents' developmental needs. Several large-scale research programs have focused attention on qualities needed in classrooms and school in order to enhance student achievement and motivation. School environments that do indeed provide a more appropriate fit to the developmental needs of young adolescent students have been shown to enhance intrinsic motivation.[9;58]

After carefully analyzing of the elements of reading as well as the aspects of academic motivation, it would seem that the two may very well be linked. Despite the variety of approaches taken towards improving reading and understanding, little attention has been paid to the connection with motivation. Many teaching methods focus upon motivation as a sort of general objective.

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